

1. Why is ddc 16 edition called phoenix Schedules?

Ans:- The 16th edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification is called the "Phoenix Schedules" because it introduced a new way to revise the classification by replacing outdated Schedules with entirely new.

Explanation:- The DDC is revised to keep up with the changing world of knowledge and to fix mistakes. When Schedules become outdated, they are replaced with new classification.

History:- This edition contained a completely new schedule for Inorganic and Organic Chemistry 546-546. Phoenix Schedules have also been used in other editions, including the 17th edition for 150 Psychology, the 18th edition for 340 Law and 510 Mathematics, and the 19th edition for 301-307 Sociology and 324.

Purpose:-

The DDC is a hierarchical classification system, which means that topics are organized from the most general to the most specific.

2) Why DDC index called relative Index?

Ans

The Index to the DDC, it is called "Relative" because it shows the connection between subjects and the disciplines in which they appear. In the Schedules, Subjects are arranged within disciplines. In the Relative Index are listed alphabetically.

- **Subjects**: In the Relative Index, Subjects are listed alphabetically.
- **Disciplines**: Below each subject, the associated disciplines are listed alphabetically.
- **Arrangement**: In the Schedules, Subjects are arranged within disciplines.